

Report

D4.3 Techno-economic assessment – Executive summary

Release Status: FOR ISSUE

Author: Audrey Lopez (Genesis), Saif Sleiman (Genesis), Leandro-Henrique Sousa (Ramboll)

Date: 21 January 2025

Filename and version: CCUS-ZEN-D4.3-v2.docx

Project ID NUMBER: 101075693

CCUS ZEN - Zero Emission Network to facilitate CCUS uptake in industrial clusters
(HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-02-12)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101075693

This project has received funding from UK Research and Innovation - Innovate UK under Innovation Funding Service (ISF)

Document History

Location

This document is stored in the following location:

Filename	CCUS-ZEN-D4.3-v2.docx
Location	

Revision History

This document has been through the following revisions:

Version No.	Revision Date	Filename/Location stored:	Brief Summary of Changes
V0	28/12/2024	CCUS-ZEN-D4.3-v0.docx	-
V1	08/01/2025	CCUS-ZEN-D4.3-v1.docx	Implementation of Partners' comments
V2	21/01/2025	CCUS-ZEN-D4.3-v2.docx	Final comments implemented

Authorisation

This document requires the following approvals:

AUTHORISATION	Name	Signature	Date
WP Leader or co-leader	Xavier Millerand	Xavier Millerand 2025.01.21 17:57:14	+01'00'
Project Coordinator	Eirik Falck da Silva		

Distribution

This document has been distributed to:

Name	Title	Version Issued	Date of Issue

© CCUS ZEN Consortium, 2025

This document contains information which is proprietary to the CCUS ZEN consortium. No third-party textual or artistic material is included in the publication without the copyright holder's prior consent to further dissemination by other third parties.

Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

Disclaimer

Co-funded by the European Union and UK Research and Innovation. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or UK Research and Innovation. Neither the European Union nor UK Research and Innovation can be held responsible for them.

No industry has committed at this stage to implement the scenarios presented in the deliverable D4.3. The scenarios presented here, while based on an industrial reality on the ground, are forward-looking scenarios that explore the potential of CCUS in the Baltic and Mediterranean regions.

Table of Contents

1	Executive Summary	5
2	Introduction	7
2.1	Document Purpose	8
3	Selected CCUS Value Chains Definition	9
3.1	Baltic Sea Region CCUS Value Chain	9
3.2	Mediterranean Sea Region CCUS Value Chain	12
4	Risk Assessment	16
5	Economic Assessment	18
5.1	Methodology	18
5.2	Results	19
5.2.1	Baltic key findings.....	19
5.2.2	Mediterranean key findings	20
5.3	Sensitivities Impact	21
5.4	Discussion	23
6	Business Model	25
6.1	Stakeholders	25
6.2	Level of integration & risk allocation	25
6.3	Revenue generation mechanisms	26
6.4	Investment & Ownership Structure	26
6.5	Government involvement	27
7	Conclusion	28
8	Abbreviations	29
9	Bibliography	30

1 Executive Summary

This report is the last deliverable of the CCUS ZEN project and aims to provide a comprehensive overview of the selected CCUS value chains in the Mediterranean and Baltic regions. Indeed, the two most promising CCUS value chains in the Baltic Sea and Mediterranean Sea regions were considered for concept development including techno-economic, risks and business model assessments.

In the Mediterranean region, the proposed development of CCUS hubs around emitter clusters like Fos-Marseille (France), Tarragona and Barcelona (Spain) demonstrates the potential for shared transport and storage infrastructure. Concurrently, the Baltic project showcases a holistic approach to large-scale CO₂ removal, leveraging cross-border collaboration to capture emissions from diverse clusters across Denmark, Germany, and Sweden. The emphasis on centralised CO₂ utilisation plants and alternative utilisation scenarios underscores the importance of innovative approaches to drive the CCUS value chain forward.

Main highlights for both value chains are captured in Table 1.1.

Cost and economic analysis are utilising AACE Class 5 cost estimation methods (expected deviation -50% to +100%). Key scopes and cost exclusions are summarised in sections 3 and 5 with detailed calculations and considerations available in the CCUS ZEN reports D4.1 and D4.2 dedicated to the individual value chains definitions (Sousa et al., 2024 and Lopez et al., 2024).

Deploying both value chains will necessitate systematically addressing key challenges, such as cost, regulatory framework clarification, cross-border coordination, and public acceptance. This process requires early engagement with all stakeholders, ensuring the provision of clear, accurate, and accessible information about the project's benefits, risks, safety, and environmental measures.

Table 1.1: Key findings for Baltic and Mediterranean CCUS value chains

	Baltic	Mediterranean
Member States Involved	Denmark, Germany, Sweden	France, Spain
Number of emitters	33 (across 9 clusters)	32 (across 3 clusters)
Storage Sites	Distributed Onshore & Offshore	Single Offshore
Operating Period	2035 – 2065	2035 – 2055
Net CO ₂ Capture (Mt)	559	196
Net CO ₂ Store (Mt)	362 (<i>Note 1</i>)	196
Annual CO ₂ Capture (Mt/y)	20.1 (<i>Note 2</i>)	9.8
Annual CO ₂ Storage (Mt/y)	14	9.8
Annual CO ₂ Utilisation (Mt/y)	6.1	<i>Note 3</i> (0.4)
CCS CAPEX (M EUR)	21,266	8,050
CCS OPEX (M EUR/year)	889	343
CCS Levelised Cost (EUR/t CO ₂)	168	128
Main Barriers and Challenges	Storage site appraisal, CO ₂ revenue streams, lack of project experience, utilisation challenges, uncertainty related risks	

Note 1: Balance for utilisation

Note 2: Cumulative value including both phases of the development

Note 3: Limited utilisation rates expected under the current scenario due to the low current amount of biogenic CO₂ available for e-fuel production (less than 4% of the captured CO₂ volumes). However, a potential of CO₂ Utilisation (ranging from 4% to 30% of the captured CO₂) could be unveiled if key challenges such as availability of green hydrogen, requirements of biogenic CO₂ imposed by the regulation after 2041 are lifted.

2 Introduction

The **overall objective** of the project is to explore the potential for CCUS value chain deployment in two regions with lower maturity level for CCUS compared to the current development in the North Sea region: the Baltic Sea and the Mediterranean Sea regions.

The **CCUS ZEN mission** is to contribute to the accelerated deployment of CCUS throughout Europe. It aims to enable mutual, continuous learning between different stakeholder types and between European regions, drawing on learnings from ongoing and past projects, creating shared understanding of mission-critical implementation elements, and building a coherent ecosystem of CCUS actors in Europe able to credibly deliver the requisite contribution to European climate policy.

To achieve this, CCUS ZEN has **five objectives**:

1. **Technical mapping**: For each region, map and understand the nature and longevity of emission sources, identify transport corridors and modalities, assess cost-effective ('bankable') storage capacity in the selected regions, and define interactions between CCUS hubs-and-clusters, renewable-based integrated energy systems, and/or circular production modes.
2. **Non-technical mapping**: Identify and involve relevant end users, public authorities and social stakeholders and analyse their concerns and needs using appropriate techniques and methods from the social sciences and humanities.
3. **Value chain scenarios**: Elaborate detailed plans for the integration of CCUS in hubs and clusters linked to CO₂ storage sites via hubs, pipeline networks and shipping routes, with due attention to national and border-crossing permits and regulatory issues.
4. **Local business model**: Perform initial impact assessment and develop local business models for delivery of CO₂ capture, transport, utilisation and/or storage, including the separation of responsibilities across the CO₂ value chain.
5. **Knowledge sharing, dissemination, and communication** : Facilitate the exchange of knowledge and know-how across CCUS projects, by continuing the activities of the existing European CCUS project network.

The five objectives are integrated in the project framework illustrated in Figure 2.1. Technical and non-technical mapping constitute a high-level regional screening of CCUS opportunities in the two CCUS ZEN regions. This is followed by a selection and analyses of the four most promising value chains in both regions. Based on the analyses, the most promising CCUS value chains in each region are selected for further development, including technical definition, risk assessment and local business models. The work throughout the project is supported by knowledge sharing, dissemination and communication with network partners and other relevant stakeholders. More information can be found online at the CCUS website: <http://www.ccuszen.eu/>.

Figure 2.1 CCUS ZEN framework for CCUS value chain development

2.1 Document Purpose

This document is the last report of the CCUS ZEN project and feeds **Objectives 3 (Value Chain Scenarios) and 4 (Local Business Model)** of the project. Previously, four potential CCUS networks were mapped for each of the two regions – the Baltics and the Mediterranean, for preliminary technical evaluation and value chain comparison. The most promising option in each region, tailored to its unique characteristics, was then selected (CCUS ZEN Report D3.3 (Shogenova et al., 2024)) to enable a more robust definition including technical, economic analysis, risks and business model aspects.

This report aims to summarise the comprehensive analysis of the selected CCUS value chains based on preliminary information available to the Consortium to-date, subject to further research and validation. Consolidating key insights from the two detailed CCUS ZEN reports D4.1 (Sousa et al., 2024) and D4.2 (Lopez et al., 2024), it seeks to offer an overarching assessment of the CCUS ZEN project's outcomes, and potential impacts. Readers of this report will gain a deeper understanding of the developments in CCUS deployment within the Baltic and Mediterranean regions, highlighting essential elements for advancing CCUS technologies in these areas.

3 Selected CCUS Value Chains Definition

3.1 Baltic Sea Region CCUS Value Chain

The value chain schematic is represented in Figure 3.1. This chain encompasses nine emitters' clusters, across Germany, Denmark, and Sweden and eight potential geological storage locations, both onshore and offshore. In Germany, it includes three industrial clusters situated in Bremen, Hannover, and Hamburg. Sweden hosts the Gothenburg cluster. Denmark contributes with a quintet of clusters located in Aalborg, Aarhus, West Midtjylland, Fredericia, and Esbjerg.

Figure 3.1 CCUS ZEN selected value chain for Baltic Sea Region

Note: Natura 2000 areas are not shown on the map but are well documented by the Miljøstyrelsen (Environmental Protection Agency in Denmark). In the current concept, the main offshore pipeline is assumed to be a repurposed natural gas pipeline and is therefore not expected to lead to any major impact on the environment.

Table 3.1 summarises the phase-wise expected operational design basis and outcomes of the project. Over the project lifespan of 30 years, limited by the net storage capacity, a total of 5 39 Mt of CO₂ will be captured and transported, of which, 362 Mt will be geologically stored.

Table 3.1 Baltic CCUS Value Chain Design Basis

Phase	Operational Period	CO ₂ Capture & Transport (Mt/y)			CO ₂ Storage (Mt/y)	CO ₂ Utilisation (Mt/y)	
1	2035 - 2045	13.7			8.2	5.5	
2*	2045 - 2065	20.1			14.0	6.1	Germany (Bremen): 3.20
		Germany 10.66 (5.59 biogenic)	Denmark 5.53 (1.82 biogenic)	Sweden 3.95 (0.65 biogenic)			Denmark (Aalborg): 1.66
							Sweden (Gothenburg): 1.19

* Phase 2 represents cumulative estimates inclusive of Phase 1

Emission clusters

The nine identified clusters comprised of thirty-three individual emission sources in total from the Power, Cement, Waste-to-Energy, Hydrogen, Refinery, Chemicals and Biomass CHP sectors, are currently accounting for 22.7 Mt maximum annual CO₂ emissions. The emission level is assumed to remain the same by the onset of the CCUS operations in 2035, as limited means of decarbonisation was one of the criteria for the chosen emitters. About 20.1 Mt/y (million tonnes per year) of these emissions is expected to be captured, limited by the capture technology efficiency of 95%, with the remainder being released into the atmosphere. The captured CO₂ will be conditioned to final purity, typically around 99%, in gas phase at 30 barg, which can be further processed for high pressure (120 barg) pipeline transportation in dense phase or at low/medium pressure (10/20 barg) for truck, barge or ship transportation.

Twenty emitters were categorised as “front runners” and thirteen as “followers”, depending on whether they were better suited for an accelerated adoption of CCUS solutions or more likely to be attracted by an established CCUS infrastructure and matured market, respectively. The development of the CCUS network was divided in two phases, first with the exclusive participation of the “front runners” in Phase 1 starting 2035 and afterwards with the inclusion of the “followers” in Phase 2, 2045.

Storage sites

Eight storage sites were selected for this region as detailed in the CCUS ZEN report D3.1 (Shogenova et al., 2024), based on geographic location and storage readiness level.

- Five of these storage sites are located offshore, from which two (Bifrost and Greensand) have been awarded with an exploration license for CO₂ storage. It is anticipated that the offshore sites Inez, Jammerbugt, and Lisa could be soon proposed for licensing.

- The remaining three are located onshore, in the Jutland region of Denmark, where one (Gassum) has also been awarded with an exploration license. The awarded storage sites with exploration licenses are under appraisal. In a related development, the onshore Thorning site has undergone a new round of tendering, with the expectation of a licence being granted by the beginning of 2025. Voldum's (onshore) potential inclusion in forthcoming licensing rounds is plausible, due to its geological characteristics, which are believed to be similar to the Gassum formation, given their proximity.

With a net anticipated mean theoretical capacity to store more than 928 million tonnes of CO₂, the eight geological sites are estimated to allow a maximum yearly storage capability of 15.1 million tonnes over 30 years limited by the technical specifications of the formations.

Utilisation

As mentioned above, the annual storage rate is lower than the estimated capture rate due to the geological parameters of the formations. Therefore, CO₂ utilisation plays a crucial role to ensure that the captured emissions meet a balanced demand. Three different utilisation hubs, one in each Member State, were identified to cater regionally, as indicated in Table 3.1.

Value chain definition

The proposed CCUS value chain can therefore be divided into three infrastructural blocks:

- The Bremen CCU cluster being isolated from the rest of the cluster will send the totality of captured emissions to the local utilisation hub.
- Emitters in the Gothenburg cluster are also planned to send part of their CO₂ for utilisation within the Swedish cluster. The remaining CO₂ not utilised will be shipped for offshore subsea injection.
- The German-Danish segment of the Baltic project comprises emitters with individual or cluster compression systems for transport pipelines carrying supercritical/dense phase CO₂, including an offshore pipeline segment to transport CO₂ to the Bifrost subsea storage site, reusing an existing pipeline corridor. Part of the collected CO₂ will be sent to the Aalborg utilisation hub, or off-shore storage sites. The remaining fraction of the captured CO₂ will be sent to Esbjerg to be liquefied and shipped to offshore storage sites. Emitters in the Esbjerg vicinity will directly transport their CO₂ to the harbour in gas phase.

3.2 Mediterranean Sea Region CCUS Value Chain

The Mediterranean value chain represented in Figure 3.2 comprises three clusters of emitters and one storage site offshore Spain. Two of the industrial clusters are located in Spain: the Tarragona cluster and the Barcelona cluster, the third one being located in France: the Fos-Marseille cluster. To be noted that the Lyon cluster (France) may be appended to the Mediterranean value chain in the future, but it is not taken into present considerations.

Figure 3.2 CCUS ZEN Selected Value Chain for Mediterranean Sea Region

Table 3.2 summarises the design basis and operational outcomes of the project. Over the project lifespan of 20 years, a total of around 200 Mt of CO₂ will be captured, transported and geologically stored corresponding to the geological storage's capacity. Limited utilisation rates are expected under the current scenario due to the low current amount of biogenic CO₂ available for e-fuel production. However, a potential of CO₂ Utilisation (ranging from 4% to 30% of the captured CO₂) could be unveiled if key challenges such as availability of green hydrogen, requirements of biogenic CO₂ imposed by the regulation after 2041 are lifted.

Table 3.2 Mediterranean CCUS Value Chain design basis

Country	Cluster	Number of emitters	CO ₂ Capture, Transport & Storage (Mt/y)	Possible CO ₂ Utilisation* (Mt/y)
Spain	Tarragona	5	1.98	0.001 - 0.59
	Barcelona	9	2.25	0.23 - 0.72
France	Fos-Marseille	18	5.54	0.21 - 1.76
Total		32	9.77	0.44 - 3.07

* Corresponding to current share of biogenic CO₂ on lower end (around 4% of the total captured CO₂) and the targets stated by the Communication from the Commission titled 'Towards an ambitious Industrial Carbon Management for the EU' (European Commission, 2024) on higher end (30% of the total captured CO₂).

Emission clusters

The three identified emission clusters comprise thirty-two individual emission sources, with five in Tarragona involving mainly refineries and chemical plants, nine in Barcelona, predominantly power generation and cement industries, and eighteen in the Fos-Marseille cluster with a more diverse set of emitters such as power, refineries, chemical and iron & steel plants. These clusters, in aggregate, currently account for a maximum CO₂ emission of 23.8 Mt/y as per 2022 data – Report D3.1 (Shogenova et al., 2024), with a selection threshold of 100 kt/y for individual emitters. Unlike the emitters selected in the Baltic value chain, the Mediterranean emitters, in consideration, are expected to deploy a multi-modal approach to decarbonise their operations including electrification, fuel switching, process optimisation, energy recovery, etc. Consequently, in line with IEA reports (IEA, 2020), EU policies, and national regulations, the potential scope of CCUS from these emitters was assessed at 9.77 Mt/y by the onset of operations in 2035 detailed in Report D3.1 (Shogenova et al., 2024).

Storage site

The proposed geological storage site is located offshore Tarragona in the Ebro Basin (Spain) with first estimations of the storage net capacity potential of around 200 Mt of CO₂. Consequently, the project life is expected to be 20 years, constrained by the net storage capacity and the corresponding annual volume of CO₂ to be stored (9.8 Mt/y). The exploration licensing for the storage site is underway, awaiting permits and hence, yet to be developed.

Utilisation

Unlike the Baltic Sea region value chain, the current share of biogenic CO₂ in net emissions is limited in the Mediterranean value chain. Consequently, the demand for captured CO₂ from the utilisation market will likely be limited owing to current policies favouring utilisation of biogenic CO₂ over that from fossil fuels in the future. Therefore, the annual geological storage rate was designed to match the carbon capture rate of 9.77 Mt/y to allow emitters a viable avenue to manage their captured CO₂. Nonetheless, multiple scenarios for utilisation rates ranging from 4% to 30% could be considered, approximately corresponding to the current share of biogenic CO₂, on one hand, and the targets stated by the Communication from the Commission titled ‘Towards an ambitious Industrial Carbon Management for the EU’ (Commission, 2024), on the other. National and international regulations will play a dominant role in determining the future course in this respect and, also, in unlocking utilisation market potential.

The amount of CO₂ directed to utilisation will be driven by several factors such as: technical maturity of the solution, availability of hydrogen and renewable energies, CO₂ nature (biogenic or fossil), cost considerations, etc. Similar to the Baltic value chain, the project proposes centralised CO₂ utilisation plants near each cluster's gathering station.

Value chain definition

To facilitate the collection of CO₂ from various sources within each cluster, a local gathering network is planned prior to long distance CO₂ transport to the geological storage site. This network transports the CO₂ in gaseous phase via pipelines specifically designed for this purpose. Beyond the CO₂ collection at the cluster level, two technical alternatives were considered for the Transportation System up to the storage site – Reference Case and Alternative Case, as illustrated in Figure 3.3.

Figure 3.3 Transportation scenarios for Mediterranean CCUS Value Chain
(a) Reference Case (b) Alternative Case

In the Reference Case, an onshore gathering hub at Tarragona is proposed to centralise CO₂ collection from three clusters: from local emitters in Tarragona, from Barcelona via an offshore pipeline, and from Fos-Marseille by ship. CO₂ can then be piped offshore from Tarragona to subsea injection wells 60 km away. Note, the CO₂ shipping facility from Fos-Marseille is already a part of the EU-designated PCI under the Callisto project.

The Alternative Case maintains the same set of emitters and storage site but differs in transportation scheme. While Tarragona emissions retain the same route to the subsea storage, emissions from Barcelona and Fos-Marseilles are directly routed to the storage site, instead of routing via Tarragona. Barcelona's CO₂ is transported by pipeline and Fos-Marseille emissions are shipped and then directly offloaded and injected via a Floating Storage and Injection Unit (FSIU).

Both cases are deemed technically feasible with the available information to-date. Further investigations are required to confirm, for example, emission volumes, pipeline routings, available footprint at the various clusters' location. The Alternative case might be less impactful on the onshore sites but will require the development of a FSIU which has not yet been deployed at industrial scale. It could prove also to be more flexible as ships from other emitting locations could offload their CO₂ directly at the injection site. This opportunity will need to be further assessed with detailed logistics evaluation.

4 Risk Assessment

A project risk assessment and initial environmental impact assessment were conducted for both value chains to ensure technical, economical, safety, environmental, and regulatory compliance. Indeed, demonstrating a comprehensive risk assessment allows to build trust with stakeholders, including investors, regulators, and the public, ensuring the successful and sustainable implementation of the CCUS project.

The risk assessment was performed through a collaborative one-day workshop with relevant project partners. This interactive session allowed for a systematic discussion on risks, their impacts, and the formulation of clear mitigation measures, setting the stage for enhanced risk management strategies moving forward.

A grouping of the risks was made according to different key topics, which include Environmental and Social Risks, Safety and Security Risks, Technical Aspects and Design Risks, Financial Aspects (Cost & Contract), Partners, Business Model & Economic Risks, and Legal and Regulatory Risks.

Key findings are summarised below. Details can be found in references CCUS ZEN reports D4.1 and D4.2 (Sousa et al., 2024 and Lopez et al., 2024):

- Environmental and Social Risks
 - Risks include habitat loss, ecosystem fragmentation, and community opposition.
 - Mitigation involves conservation efforts, stakeholder engagement, public acceptance and transparent communication.
- Safety and Security Risks
 - Risks include CO₂ leakages and toxicological impacts.
 - Mitigation involves early engagement with local communities, governments, and financial institutions to address safety concerns and ensure public acceptance. As well, defining and implementing effective leak detection systems and safety measures are recommended in the next steps.
- Technical Aspects and Design Risks
 - Highlights the need for robust technical definitions, including that for storage sites, to accommodate evolving CCUS technologies and potential challenges in CO₂ storage.
 - Detailed studies with confirmed design basis are recommended to refine technical specifications and optimise elements of the value chain, particularly in CO₂ conditioning and transport design.
- Financial Aspects (Cost & Contract), Partners, Business Model & Economic Risks
 - Risks of non-conformance and stranded investments due to technical uncertainties, emphasising the importance of realistic schedules.

- From a business perspective, an under supply of captured CO₂ or lower demand for its utilisation may significantly upset the project business plan. The economics of alternative decarbonisation path may have a significant bearing on this.
- Delayed storage appraisal will not only have a negative financial impact on the project but may have significant bearing on the business model, proving to be prohibitive in the worst-case scenario.
- Mitigation involves developing clear business models and contracting strategies to align stakeholders and secure necessary investments for decarbonisation projects. Timely execution of the project as per the planned schedule is essential.
- Legal and Regulatory Risks
 - Regulatory pace, direction, uniformity across involved Member States in alignment with EU decarbonisation policies is important. Too weak or too aggressive regulations, either way, may impede CCUS business cases.
 - Uncertainty of regulations impacting CO₂ pricing results in uncertainty of revenue streams for business stakeholders, impeding their engagement towards swift action.
 - Mitigation involves advocating for effective stakeholder engagement and management for permit approvals and alignment with regulatory entities. A balanced regulatory framework harmonising all decarbonisation means is necessary. Transparent, predictable, and steady CO₂ pricing comprehended by all stakeholders is essential to accelerate CCUS.

Different stakeholders are exposed to different risks, and a broad understanding of those across the group is necessary for an effective engagement, highlighting the importance of dissemination activities, also addressed by the CCUS ZEN project.

5 Economic Assessment

5.1 Methodology

Cost estimates (CAPEX and OPEX) were developed based on discipline specialist engineers' expertise, utilising standard design methodologies, and cost factors with the inclusion of appropriate risk margins. The estimates were structured to align with the Class 5 accuracy of the AACE International Recommended Practices leading to an accuracy range of -50% to +100%. In the cost estimation process, factors such as labour rates and cost norms, in line with international projects or references such as Technology Data from the Danish Energy Agency (Danish Energy Agency, 2024) but proprietary to Genesis and Ramboll, were considered.

Both assessments, i.e., for the Baltic and the Mediterranean regions, accounted for all aspects of project development comprehensively including CO₂ capture units, onshore terminals, transportation via pipelines, shipping, geological storage. Allowances and contingencies cover owner's costs for development, consultancy, design, project management, permitting, marketing, communications, risks, and other minor omissions.

General exclusions comprised decommissioning, land acquisition and right of way, grid expansion, modularisation & transportation to site, route surveys, brownfield modifications, customs duties, local taxes, owner's cost, client's authorization for expenditure contingency and escalation costs. Utilisation plants were consistently excluded from the cost scope, focusing instead on the transportation segment of the value chain up to the designated storage or utilisation sites. While in the Mediterranean value chain, the transportation and storage system has been designed for the whole captured emissions, in the Baltic region, the captured emissions were divided between storage and utilisation (being excluded from the cost estimate). Additionally, project specific cost assumptions were considered in the estimations, such as the geographic restriction to the Baltic/Mediterranean regions, or the appraisal confirmation of all selected storage sites which reflect the early-stage maturity of these projects. The estimations aim, therefore, to provide a reasonable cost level of magnitude, which should be further validated as projects mature. Additional details on the scope of cost estimation are presented in CCUS ZEN Reports D4.1 and D4.2 (Sousa et al., 2024 and Lopez et al., 2024). They also enlist all elements of OPEX associated with each operation for the Baltic and the Mediterranean value chains, respectively.

The Levelised Cost (LC) of both value chains was assessed reflecting the minimum price per tonne of CO₂ necessary to cover capture, transport, and storage expenses while ensuring a return on invested capital, aiding in assessing economic viability. This metric was calculated by dividing the present value of total costs by the present value of total CO₂ captured and stored over the projected operational period (30 years for the Baltic case and 20 years for Mediterranean case). Based on the literature review and inhouse experience with carbon capture and storage projects, a nominal discount rate of 8% pre-tax and 0% cost inflation over the 2024 price-reference were applied for the purposes of the economic model. Note, in the technoeconomic analysis of the Baltic case, the discounting principle was applied from the current year, i.e., 2024, simulating a pre-FID allocation. On the other hand, in the Mediterranean case, it was applied from the start of project development, i.e., 2030, aligned

with the principle of capital allotment as per the expenditure schedule. Consequently, the net present values in the Baltic case depend both on the project-life and the development start date, whereas in the Mediterranean case, the latter has no impact.

5.2 Results

The cost estimates are assumed to the AACE level 5 with -50% / +100% accuracy with limited input data available and preliminary engineering definitions which are to be further validated in future development phases. Costs for respectively Baltic and Mediterranean Sea are based on different concepts, sources and assumptions and therefore not fully comparable.

5.2.1 Baltic key findings

The costs were organised per technical block as shown in Figure 5.1.

Total CAPEX (sum of Phase 1 and 2) and OPEX per investment phase, as explained in Section 3.1, were calculated according to the captured CO₂ and necessary infrastructure. In Phase 1, the investments required to operate the CO₂ from the “front runners” was considered. In Phase 2, all the emitters and associated infrastructure were considered. Phase 1 was set to start operation by 2035. Phase 2 was assumed to start operation on 2045. The economic analysis was developed up to the year of 2065, leading to a maximum operational time of 30 years.

Costs are mostly concentrated on the CO₂ Capture units. To a lesser extent, CAPEX is also influenced by the pipeline costs (since the transport system is mainly a pipeline system). Developer’s costs for engineering, consultancy, project management, design, and administration, included in the allowance, and contingency are an equally important CAPEX factor. Regarding OPEX, besides the CO₂ capture units, the geological storage is an important cost factor, as well as the onshore terminals since they are energy intensive infrastructure.

Net present value of total costs (NPC) and levelised cost (LC) of a project, both inclusive of all CAPEX and OPEX, are two key financial indicators for its feasibility from a business case perspective. The current assessment of the Baltic CCS value chain revealed:

- a total CAPEX of 21,266 M EUR and an OPEX of 646 M EUR/y from 2035 to 2045 and of 889 M EUR/y from 2045 to 2065.
- an NPC of 12,809 M EUR as of 2024, with an estimated 559 Mt of net CO₂ captured and transported, and 362 Mt stored, over 30 years.
- an LC of 168 EUR/ton of CO₂ as of 2024, with 78 EUR for CO₂ capture and 54 EUR for transport and storage, while the remaining cost is a reserved budget for risks and unknowns (contingency and allowance).

Note, the costs associated to CO₂ utilisation and the revenue stream from sales in the utilisation market are not accounted in the economic calculations presented here. Further details on calculation methods and reported values may be found in Report D4.1 (Sousa et al., 2024).

Figure 5.1 Relative Net Present Cost distribution for the Baltic value chain

5.2.2 Mediterranean key findings

Figure 5.2 summarises the CAPEX and OPEX distribution for the two cases studied for the Mediterranean CCS value-chain over its estimated service period of 20 years. Onshore transport includes on land pipelines, terminals, and compression facilities, whereas offshore transport includes shipping and subsea pipelines. Appropriate contingencies and allowances are built-in within each block, at about 30% of CAPEX.

Figure 5.2 Relative Net Present Cost distribution for the Mediterranean value chain

Again, costs are mostly concentrated on the CO₂ capture units and transport pipelines, as in the case of the Baltic region. The Mediterranean value chain assessment revealed:

- a total CAPEX of 8,050 M EUR and an OPEX of 343 M EUR/y for the Reference case.
- a total CAPEX of 8,186 M EUR and an OPEX of 344 M EUR/y for the Alternative case.
- an NPC of 8,557 M EUR for the Reference case or 8,665 M EUR for the Alternative case, considering an annual discount rate of 8% from the start of project development in 2030 and an estimated 196 Mt of CO₂ captured and stored over lifetime of 20 years.
- an LC of 128 EUR/t of CO₂ for the Reference case as of 2030, with 58 EUR for CO₂ capture and 70 EUR for transport & storage. The LC for the Alternative case is higher by 2 EUR/t of CO₂ owing to the increased transport costs.

Further details on calculations and reported values may be found in the CCUS ZEN Report D4.2 (Lopez et al., 2024).

5.3 Sensitivities Impact

As part of the economic assessment within each value chain, sensitivity analyses were conducted to comprehend the diverse impacts by investigating how deviation in individual variables affect costs while maintaining other factors constant.

In the Baltic region, the uncertainty on CAPEX is one of the main factors to consider, when assessing the levelised cost variation. Changes of +/-20% on CAPEX can result in changes of +/-16% on the levelised cost, resulting in a range of 145 to 195 EUR/tCO₂ with a base case reference price of 168 EUR/tCO₂. The variations of the discount rate can also lead to high impacts on the LC. Other factors that affect the OPEX have a lower impact on the overall cost indicators but must be monitored.

In the Mediterranean case, the analysis demonstrates that among the four parameters tested CO₂ volume has the highest impact on the value-chains viability, followed by CAPEX, discount rate and OPEX. For example, changes of +20% on CO₂ volumes can result in changes of +25% on the levelised cost, resulting in LC up to 160 EUR/tCO₂.

Given the preliminary stage of the project, several assumptions have been made to conduct the current analysis. The table below outlines examples of risks related to the project's uncertainties that could affect the cost estimates.

Table 5.1 Example of risks impacting the current cost estimates

Type	Risk	Mitigation
Design Basis and Specifications	Modification of input data (e.g. CO ₂ emissions volumes, location, storage capacity, subsea layout ...)	Refine design basis by more specific studies and more detailed discussions with emitters, storage owners regarding their future strategy linked to CCUS
CO ₂ Capture and Conditioning	Underestimated or overestimated plot space.	Carry out dedicated studies and sites assessments with emitters
	Brownfield modification complexity for the existing facility emitter (site clearance, connections, lower productivity...)	Strategy of CO ₂ conditioning to be defined per cluster depending on the transportation schemes,
	No availability of electricity from grid to fence boundary	
	Uncertainty of CO ₂ composition from each emitter impacting treatment required	
CO ₂ Transport	Preliminary pipeline & cable routings: potential deviations due to urban environment, bathymetry, other infrastructure, obstructions Nature 2000 etc	
CO ₂ Shipping	Unavailability of relevant ship design from 3rd parties	Early engagement with ship owners and shipping industry stakeholders
	No availability or limited size of existing jetty (Fos-Marseille, Tarragona).	Carry out dedicated studies (i.e. Jetty Detailed Sizing) in the next project phase
	Brownfield modifications requirements	
Infrastructure for Subsea Injection	Well Count uncertainty leading to increased number of injection wells required	Carry out dedicated studies for reservoir characterization in the next project phase. Engage discussions with storage site owners and operators
Geological Reservoir	Risk of lower reservoir capacity than planned	Carry out dedicated studies in the next project phase. Engage discussions with storage site owners and operators
	Reservoir pressure increase up to the fracturing pressure resulting in brine production	
Drilling	Drilling complexity: well may need to be abandoned and side tracked.	Carry out dedicated studies in the next project phase and build on return on experience from past drilling operations that have already been made for O&G operation
	More well interventions to be planned.	Carry out dedicated studies in the next project phase

While the order of sensitivity sets the priority in terms of addressing respective risks and uncertainties at later stages of the project, it is important to note that sensitivity varies across the segments of the value-chain. For instance, sensitivity to CAPEX level varies between carbon capture units and transport & storage segments, with the latter being more affected by change in CAPEX. This reveals difference in relative importance of uncertainties and risks across segments and subsegments of the value-chain. These differences should be accounted for and addressed by the business model and underlying principles for the terms and conditions of commercial contracts to be concluded between the value-chain players.

Many of the risks described in Section 3 may also cause project delays. This can be mitigated with a longer investment period, i.e., distributing the expenses towards the back end of the project while retaining the facilities commissioning and operational dates. This would significantly lower the estimated costs. However, postponing project delivery dates would negatively impact the revenue streams, while prolonging the carbon tax payment period or market compliance costs, which could be fiscally prohibitive for the development of the CCUS networks.

5.4 Discussion

CCUS technoeconomic studies, as for any capital project, are largely dependent on assumptions and exclusions, which affect cost estimates. Hence, they should not be compared without taking those differences into account. Consequently, the present study may not be directly comparable to those for other projects. Moreover, regional specificities introduce another layer of divergences. Therefore, Baltic and the Mediterranean value chains presented herein may have very different business cases compared to similar projects from the United Kingdom, the Netherlands, or Norway. As a matter of fact, even in this study, the two value chains cannot be compared like-for-like. However, this subsection addresses some of the common features of the two.

First and foremost, this assessment suggested the technoeconomic feasibility and associated limitations of both projects. The levelised cost of CCS predominantly depends on the category of participating industries, which in turn determines the CO₂ concentration in their emission (the higher the concentration, the lower the LC of capture) , and the cost of CO₂ transport network. Evidently, both value chains seem to demonstrate a competitive position in terms of levelised costs, positioning them favourably. However, in such early stages of the projects, there are still many uncertainties and risks, which may result in cost escalation. Nonetheless, the present study sets a path for describing these two potential large-scale CCUS networks. The cost could be expected to decrease as the CCS industry develops in the future. Key factors that could participate in reducing costs include economies of scale, the number of projects undertaken, the potential repurposing of existing infrastructure and the development of standards allowing the deployment of an efficient supply chain.

The Emission Trading System (ETS) allowance price, summed with applicable costs related to applied carbon taxes, are a first order indicator of the minimum levelised cost needed for economic sustainability of projects. However, other financial parameters like subsidies or incentives for CCUS, market prices, other forms of avoided carbon taxes, etc., must be factored in.

Secondly, regarding monetisation of the captured CO₂ through utilisation or appropriate credit mechanisms, EU policies and Member State regulations will play a critical role in creating a demand market for the captured CO₂ through appropriate incentives. E-fuels, especially e-SAF and e-methanol, are expected to be key demand sectors, considering EU policies promoting RFNBOs in the latest edition of the Renewable Energy Directive (RED) III, published in 2023. In this regard, the promotion of RFNBO, which necessitates biogenic CO₂ as a feedstock by 2041, has a second order benefit in accelerating the demand for biofuels. Beyond energy applications, CCU also holds promise for material applications, such as mineralisation. On the storage front, in case the CO₂ capture and storage demands from the considered clusters fail to meet the expectations, geological sites developed for receiving CO₂ shipments under these projects may also be utilised by other signee Member States of the London Protocol, which will likely improve the economics of the currently considered projects.

However, it is important to be mindful that in a competitive market for decarbonisation, CCUS must have an economic edge against other alternatives for viability. Apart from regulatory consistency, time is a crucial parameter in deciding the profitability of projects. Project execution delays will not only increase implementation costs but may also result in asset depreciation and emitters preferring alternative decarbonisation routes in a quickly shifting domain.

6 Business Model

Though CCUS is an important pathway to industrial decarbonisation for the EU to attain its climate goals, its success relies on a robust business model with long-term prospects of profitability that is flexible enough to accommodate both technical and non-technical uncertainties. This in turn is influenced by several factors like technological innovation, regulatory alignment, and strategic partnerships. The focus lies on leveraging these factors to transform CO₂ into a tradable commodity to create new revenue streams for industries. Nonetheless CCUS projects should also be designed as a public good, justifying significant scope for supportive government intervention rather than exclusively relying on market mechanisms. Business models synergising both regulatory and market aspects of CCUS are key to accelerated deployment. CCUS ZEN focused on identifying and comparing applicable options such as, level of integration & risk allocation, revenue generation mechanisms, investment and ownership structure, and government involvement for the two regional value chains considered.

6.1 Stakeholders

As in most energy and climate projects, a large and diverse set of stakeholders are involved in the CCUS value chain. Broadly, these stakeholders would include regulatory authorities from both EU and national level, NGOs, financial institutions, project developers/partners, emitting industries, aggregators, and transport and storage operators. Involving all of them, taking their individual interests into account, and ensuring a transparent communication channel to foster mutual trust are imperative for the successful implementation of CCUS projects. Such engagement ensures regulatory compliance and secures financial support for these projects in a collaborative environment. For optimal outcome, it is also important to understand the domain, extent, and order of involvement of the different stakeholders in these multidisciplinary and multi-party projects.

6.2 Level of integration & risk allocation

Drawing from past experiences, four broad business models that are typical of energy markets, were considered:

1. Fully integrated model across the value chain, where a single service provider manages all aspects of the value chain, from CO₂ capture to storage.
2. Partial single hub model, where the transportation and storage infrastructure are owned and operated by a single entity, with multiple entities responsible for CO₂ capture. This includes scenarios where emitters are responsible for their CO₂ capture, with another entity handling transportation, utilisation, and storage.
3. Partial multi-hub model, where multiple entities handle CO₂ capture and supply to an Aggregator, which negotiates agreements with emitters and transportation and storage operator(s). This includes scenarios where capture is provided as a service, enhancing flexibility, but requiring interface regularisation with transportation and storage services through an aggregator.

4. Partial free market model, where multiple transportation and storage options are available with capacity freely marketed, allowing emitters to select preferred providers on a competitive basis. This includes scenarios where CO₂ transport and/or utilisation is provided as a service, with specialised entities competing to handle captured CO₂.

While both regions explored similar integration models, the Mediterranean value chain emphasised the variability in emitter profiles and emission source requirements, guiding the selection of single-hub and multi-hub integration models. The Baltic value chain, on the other hand, had a greater emphasis on CO₂ utilisation potential across hubs and optimal transport network, owing to the project size and complexity, advocating for hub-based structures and clear definitions of stakeholder roles and engagement within the value chain.

6.3 Revenue generation mechanisms

Robust revenue generation mechanisms are essential for viable CCUS projects, with emitters needing diverse income sources to cover their operational costs, generate returns on invested capital, and manage financial risks within CCUS networks. Potential revenue streams encompass compliance markets like ETS, voluntary carbon markets, tax credits from emission curtailments and associated measures, other government incentives, CO₂ sales as a commodity, and low-carbon product premiums. The EU ETS market volatility plays a pivotal role, prompting emitters to balance their investment in emission reduction mechanisms and carbon allowances. Voluntary carbon markets offer monetisation avenues to even those sectors that are not covered under the ETS. Leveraging various revenue sources is crucial for not only reducing greenhouse gases but also creating profitable opportunities in the low-carbon economy. Hence, stakeholders, especially emitting industries, must develop a multi-pronged strategic roadmap balancing all approaches. Government incentives like direct subsidies and project grants, promoting well established hedging mechanisms like Contracts for Difference (CfD) in the carbon market, and long-term off-taker agreements will play a crucial role in supporting CCUS technology development and deployment. However, given the infancy of national regulatory frameworks for carbon markets in most Member States, governments have a key role to play.

6.4 Investment & Ownership Structure

Ownership models are classified into public-owned, mixed public-private, and private-owned. The ownership type determines the level of investment required and the extent of government control. There is a necessity for government involvement for funding, coordination, and risk mitigation. They play a crucial role in shaping effective CCUS ownership models. Nonetheless, collaboration between industry and the public sector is vital for establishing critical infrastructure. Thus, ownership models striking a balance between public oversight and market efficiency are essential for accelerated deployment of CCUS technologies and achieving broader climate goals.

6.5 Government involvement

Government involvement in the advancement of CCUS networks is crucial and can be categorised into several key areas. Broadly, its role is to provide policy support facilitating the establishment of additional revenue streams to offset CCUS costs and directly invest in these projects until the market matures. Financial incentives such as carbon pricing, grants, tax credits, and loan guarantees play a significant role in achieving the same. Infrastructure development led by governments is essential for establishing transportation networks and storage sites critical for the effective functioning of CCUS networks. Successful cases in countries like Denmark and Norway highlight the necessity of substantial government support, ranging from legal permissibility to financing assistance, to ensure the viability of CCUS infrastructure projects and overcome regulatory challenges. For instance, the Danish Government supports the development of CCS via three direct support mechanisms with considerable financial support to projects in order to support the industry to bring down cost to market conditions. Four different license rounds for respectively offshore, onshore and nearshore storage sites have been launched and so far, three offshore and three onshore licenses for exploration have been granted. The first offshore storage made FID in late 2024.

Governments must integrate long-term sector-specific mandates in their policy and regulatory frameworks associated to climate goals. This would signal clarity to the private sector, which in turn, would drive CCUS adoption optimally. Public-private partnerships are instrumental in accelerating CCUS development by sharing risks and co-investing in infrastructure. Research initiatives, education programs, and international collaborations supported by governments create a conducive environment for CCUS progress.

Public acceptance is a key factor, with stakeholder engagement playing a crucial role in highlighting the benefits of CCUS projects for local economies and climate goals, ultimately ensuring the success of CCUS initiatives.

7 Conclusion

The assessment reports on the Mediterranean and Baltic Sea regions highlight promising opportunities for CCUS initiatives with respect to impact and techno-economic viability. In the Mediterranean region, the proposed development of CCUS hubs around emitter clusters like Fos-Marseille, Tarragona, and Barcelona demonstrates the potential for shared transport and storage infrastructure, fostering public-private partnerships and attracting investments. The emphasis on centralised CO₂ utilisation plants and alternative utilisation scenarios underscores the importance of innovative approaches to drive the CCUS value chain forward.

Concurrently, the Baltic project showcases a holistic approach to large-scale CO₂ removal, leveraging cross-border collaboration to capture emissions from diverse clusters across Denmark, Germany, and Sweden. The project's design basis, encompassing capture units, onshore terminals, pipeline networks, and geological storage delineation, sets a solid foundation for efficient project execution. Key financial indicators, inclusive of revenue streams such as CO₂ utilisation and government incentives, could suggest economic viability of the project, while a well-defined business model would ensure its sustainability.

The chosen CCUS networks could be potential candidates for future EU PCI (Projects of Common Interest) provided a larger involvement of the stakeholders. A recent example is the Callisto (CARbon LIquefaction transportation and STOrage) project which has been designated as an EU PCI and includes the Ravenna CO₂ storage hub in the Adriatic Sea off the coast of Italy.

Both regions face common challenges, including addressing high costs and risks, creating markets through regulatory frameworks, and providing long-term policy certainty to incentivise CCUS adoption. Coordination among stakeholders and the need for robust business cases underscore the importance of harmonised regulatory frameworks and effective cross-border coordination to realise the full potential of CCUS value chains in the Mediterranean and Baltic Sea regions.

To succeed, these initiatives require flexible business models sensitive to market complexities and stakeholder engagement. By addressing key challenges systematically and with comprehensive policy support at Member State and EU levels, the Mediterranean and Baltic Sea CCUS projects can play a pivotal role in advancing decarbonisation efforts, laying the groundwork for a sustainable low-carbon economy in the respective regions.

8 Abbreviations

AACE	American Association of Cost Engineering
CAPEX	Capital Expenditure
CCUS	Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage
CfD	Contracts-for-difference
CU	CO ₂ Utilisation
ETS	Emissions Trading System
EU	European Union
EUR	Euro (currency)
FID	Financial Investment Decision
FOAK	First-of-a-kind
FSIU	Floating Storage and Injection Unit
IEA	International Energy Agency
LC	Levelised Cost
Mt	Million ton
Mt/y	Million ton per year
NPC	Net Present Cost
OPEX	Operating Expenditure
PCI	Project of Common Interest
PV	Present Value
RFNBO	Renewable Fuels of Non-Biological Origin
SAF	Sustainable Aviation Fuel
T&S	Transport and Storage

9 Bibliography

- Danish Energy Agency (2024). Technology Data – Carbon Capture, Transport and Storage. First published November 2021, Version 3 (April 2024), ISBN 978-87-94447-14-0.
- European Commission. (2024). Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions. Towards an ambitious Industrial Carbon Management for the EU, Retrieved online: <https://eur-lex.europa>.
- IEA. (2020). *Special Report on Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage, CCUS in the transition to net-zero emissions*. Energy Technology Perspectives 2020.
- Larry R. D, P. R. (2020). *Cost Estimate Classification System - As Applied For The Petroleum Exploration And Production Industry*. AACE International Recommended Practice No. 87R-14.
- Larry R. D., P. R. (2017). *Cost Estimate Classification System - As Applied In Engineering, Procurement, And Construction For The Process Industries*. AACE International Recommended Practice No. 18R-97.
- Lopez, A., Koumentis, I., Ouarab, Z.A., Avsar, M., Perimenis, A., Bouvier, L., Gravaud, I., Ombudstvedt, I., Warmer, L., Honegger, M., Pollara, M. (2024). *D4.2 Detailed plan for development of the most promising CCUS value chain in the Mediterranean Region*. Open report in EU Horizon Europe CCUS ZEN. Project 101075693.
- Lothe, A.E., Gravaud, I., Falck da Silva, E., Skagestad, R., Shogenova, A., Shogenov, K., Sousa, L.H., Wójcicki, A., Sınayuç, Ç., Yıldırım, B., Bulbul, S., Perimenis, A., Bouvier, L. (2024). *Deliverable 1.3 A framework for regional high-level technical screening of promising CCUS value chains*. Open report in EU Horizon Europe CCUS ZEN. Project 101075693.
- Mengden, A. (2024). *Tax Foundation, Europe: Carbon Taxes in Europe 2024*. Retrieved from <https://taxfoundation.org/data/all/eu/carbon-taxes-europe-2024/>
- Ringstad, C., Falck da Silva, E., Skagestad, R., Heyn, R., Biragnet, C., Frykman P., Anthonsen, K.L., Gravaud, I., Wójcicki, A., Shogenova, A., Shogenov, K., Sınayuç, Ç., Yıldırım, B., Bulbul, S., Sousa, L.H. & Perimenis, A. (2023). *D 1.1: High-level regional mapping of CO2 emission sources utilization industry and infrastructure in the Baltic Sea and Mediterranean Sea regions*. CCUS ZEN.
- Shogenova, A., Shogenov, K., Sousa, L.H., Bonto, M., Gravaud, I., Lopez, A., Koumentis, I., Sınayuç, Ç., Yıldırım, B., Bulbul, S., Frykman P., Anthonsen, K.L., Bouvier, L., Lothe, A., Wójcicki, A., Perimenis, A., Ombudstvedt, I., Ostgaard, L.W., Honegger, M., Karimi, F., & Marzban, E. (2024), *Deliverable 3.1 CCUS value chains for the two CCUS ZEN regions selected for further development in WP4*. Open report in EU Horizon Europe CCUS ZEN. Project 101075693.
- Shogenova, A., Shogenov, K., Sousa, L.H., Bonto, M., Gravaud, I., Sınayuç, Ç., Yıldırım, B., Bulbul, S., Frykman P., Anthonsen, K.L., Bouvier, L., Lothe, A., Wójcicki, A., Perimenis, A., Ombudstvedt, I., Ostgaard, L.W., Honegger, M., Karimi, F., &

Marzban, E. (2024). *D3.3 A generic framework for selection of the most promising CCUS value chains*. Open report in EU Horizon Europe CCUS ZEN. Project 101075693.

Sousa, L.H., Johannesen, J. H., Davatgar, E.B., Brown, J., Warmer, L., Ombudstvedt, I., Perimenis, A., Poralla, M. (2024). *D4.1 Detailed plan for development of the most promising CCUS value chain in the Baltic Sea region*. Open report in EU Horizon Europe CCUS ZEN. Project 101075693.